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DELIVERABLE REPORT

Transnational Access to electron and proton beam testing facilities

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ABSTRACT

- The ARIES partners KIT, CEA, DESY and STFC of the work package WP11 (electron and proton beam testing) provided Transnational Access at five accelerator test facilities, named:
- ANKA/KARA @ KIT enabled 2746 hours TNA in 7 Projects for 27 users in 5 years
- FLUTE @ KIT enabled 456 hours TNA in 2 projects for 9 users in 5 years
- IPHI @ CEA enabled 72 hours TNA in 2 projects for 13 users in 4 years
- SINBAD @ DESY enabled 242 hours TNA in 2 projects for 5 users in period P3
- VELA @ STFC enables 184 hours in 4 projects for 16 users in 5 years

ARIES Consortium, 2022

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. DESCRIPTION OF INFRASTRUCTURE5

1.1 KIT-ANKA5

1.2 KIT-FLUTE5

1.3 IPHI5

1.4 SINBAD6

1.5 VELA6

1.6 DESCRIPTION OF THE SELECTION PROCEDURE6

2. SUMMARY OF TA PROVIDED7

3. HIGHLIGHTS OF TA RESULTS7

1.1 KIT-ANKA7

1.2 KIT-FLUTE8

1.3 IPHI8

1.4 SINBAD9

1.5 VELA9

4. LIST OF PUBLICATIONS LINKED TO TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS ACTIVITIES 11

ANNEX: GLOSSARY..... 13

Executive summary

The ARIES partners KIT, CEA, DESY and STFC of the work package WP11 (electron and proton beam testing) provided Transnational Access at five accelerator test facilities, they are:

The Karlsruhe Research Accelerator KARA is the storage ring of the 2.5 GeV KIT synchrotron light source at Karlsruhe, Germany, and is also operated as an accelerator test facility providing a unique test environment for accelerator R&D.

In addition, KIT operates FLUTE (Ferninfrarot Linac- Und Test Experiment), a compact and versatile linear accelerator test facility for accelerator physics and technology.

The IPHI is a prototype proton injector that accelerates a 100-mA continuous beam up to 3 MeV at CEA in Saclay, France.

SINBAD (“Short Innovative Bunches and Accelerators at DESY”) is an 160 MeV electron linac accelerator R&D facility located at the DESY lab in Hamburg, Germany.

VELA (Versatile Electron Linear Accelerator) is a high performance, modular injector facility located at the STFC Daresbury Laboratory, UK, and capable of delivering up to 250 pC of bunch charge at 6 MeV.

These ARIES partners provided the following Transnational Access at five accelerator test facilities:

ANKA/KARA @ KIT enabled 2746 hours TNA in 7 Projects for 27 users in 5 years

FLUTE @ KIT enabled 456 hours TNA in 2 projects for 9 users in 5 years

IPHI @ CEA enabled 72 hours TNA in 2 projects for 13 users in 4 years

SINBAD @ DESY enabled 242 hours TNA in 2 projects for 5 users in period P3

VELA @ STFC enables 184 hours in 4 projects for 16 users in 5 years

1. Description of infrastructure

1.1 KIT-ANKA

At Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) the electron accelerator complex consists of a 53 MeV microtron, a 500 MeV booster synchrotron and a 2.5 GeV synchrotron named KARA. This Karlsruhe Research Accelerator KARA is the storage ring of the KIT synchrotron light source and is also operated as an accelerator test facility providing a unique test environment for accelerator R&D. Accelerator studies at the KARA profit from its flexible lattice, large energy range (0.5 - 2.5 GeV), adjustable filling pattern and bunch lengths (50 ps down to a few ps in a dedicated short bunch operation mode), and the fully synchronized, fast, transversal and longitudinal beam diagnostics. The latter includes novel single-shot, high repetition rate electro-optical longitudinal bunch profile monitoring and in-house developed detector systems (e.g., THz detectors) with bunch-by-bunch and turn-by-turn multi-channel readout. At KARA the consortium, KIT and Bilfinger Noell GmbH, was the first to demonstrate full operation of the superconducting insertion devices at KARA, optimized for series production and ready for installation in synchrotron light sources and free electron lasers.

1.2 KIT-FLUTE

FLUTE (Ferninfrarot Linac- Und Test Experiment) is a compact and versatile linear accelerator test facility at KIT. Its focus is on accelerator physics and technology including systematic studies on the generation and dynamics of ultra-short electron bunches, in addition to photon science experiments with intense, ultra-short terahertz (THz) pulses. FLUTE consists of a RF photo-injector, an S-band linac and a D-shaped chicane to compress electron bunches covering a large bunch charge range, from 1 pC to 1 nC, and bunch lengths from ps range down to a few fs. FLUTE is providing short electron bunches with beam energies of 5 up to 41 MeV and is licensed up to 90 MeV. FLUTE serves as a test bench for advanced accelerator diagnostics, synchronization and stabilization schemes, reliability, and innovative instrumentation. It is envisioned to also provide intense terahertz radiation with focused electric fields up to GV/m for applications in accelerator physics, materials science, life sciences, and medicine.

1.3 IPHI

The High Intensity Proton Injector (IPHI) is a beamline located on the premises of the Accelerator, Cryogenics and Magnetism Division (DACM) at CEA in Saclay, France. The facility can be used to perform beam dynamics studies and to develop and test high intensity beam diagnostics and beam devices. IPHI features a 3 MeV proton beam with peak intensities between 1 and 100 mA and duty cycles between 1 ms / 1 Hz up to continuous mode. In addition, the facility can be used as a neutron source at low flux ($10^9 - 10^{10}$ n/s) which allows users to optimise neutron moderators, test neutron diagnostics, or use neutrons for irradiation purposes. The 352 MHz RF platform can also serve two additional vaults to perform RF test RF components (RF windows, RF power loops, DTLs, etc.)

1.4 SINBAD

SINBAD (“Short Innovative Bunches and Accelerators at DESY”) is an electron linac accelerator R&D facility located at the DESY lab in Hamburg, Germany. The facility was constructed during the ARIES TNA period and was available to users in mid of 2021. The ARES linac accelerates electron bunches of 0.1 – 200 pC charge to 160 MeV kinetic energy, compressing them to only a few fs in bunch length. These high brightness electron bunches are ideally suited for injection into advanced accelerating structures such as laser acceleration in dielectric structures and state of the art beam diagnostic tests.

ARES (Accelerator Research Experiment at SINBAD) serves also as testbed for beam stabilization, fs-level synchronization, and medical applications of electron beams.

1.5 VELA

VELA (Versatile Electron Linear Accelerator) is a high performance, modular injector facility located at the STFC Daresbury Laboratory and capable of delivering a highly stable, highly customisable, short pulse, high quality electron beam to a series of test enclosures.

The VELA facility comprises an S-Band Photo-injector, capable of delivering up to 250 pC of bunch charge at 6 MeV, with micron level beam emittance performance. The copper photocathode is driven by a UV laser which delivers a pseudo-Gaussian profile of 1 mm FWHM at the cathode. RF power is delivered to the RF Gun via a 10 MW klystron which is powered by a modulator, all of which is housed on the VELA injector enclosure roof. The electron beam is then transported through a beam diagnostics line comprising wall current monitor, pepper pot, YAG screens, Faraday Cup and slit/strip line BPMs, and a transverse deflecting cavity, before exiting into the two experimental enclosures.

1.6 DESCRIPTION OF THE SELECTION PROCEDURE

The User Group Leaders contacted the facility coordinator before beginning the formal application process to discuss the technical aspects and feasibility of the project, the suitability of the proposal’s draft and the eligibility of the user group. This resolved eligibility issues and gave feedback to rejected applicants before the formal TA application procedure. The User Group Leader downloaded, completed, and sent the ARIES TA application form to ARIES-TA@cern.ch.

Each facility, following its own selection procedure to assess technical feasibility, forwarded the recommended project for decision of the WP11 User Selection Panel (USP) based on scientific quality. Proposals were evaluated based on scientific merit whilst taking into consideration the availability of the facility and similar facilities in the users’ home country.

The partners thank the external members of the USP for their valuable evaluation work.

2. Summary of TA provided

ARIES-TA WP 11	TA units for users [h]	Projects	Users (onsite and remote)
KARA (ANKA)	2646	7	27
FLUTE	456	2	9
IPHI	72	2	13
ARES (SINBAD)	242	2	5
VELA	184	4	16

3. Highlights of TA results

1.1 KIT-ANKA

TA user projects “Optics measurements with TxT data” in the field of beam dynamics and beam diagnostic were carried by KIT based on proposals of CERN and Uppsala University. The beam dynamic measurements with the CLIC SC Wiggler were carried out at KARA. Users from Uppsala University measured the tune-shift with the wiggler’s field at KIT, users from CERN participated in experiments on tune and chromaticity measurements remotely. They used a novel method to measure chromaticity. The results agree well with the traditional chromaticity measurements. The KIT supported the experiments with a scientist and the operating team of the KIT facility. The results obtained are relevant for the design and operation of future accelerators like CLIC, ILC or ultra-low emittance rings.

In collaboration with the team of ARIES WP 7 (SOLEIL, PSI, and Oxford), working points with low and negative momentum compaction factors have been implemented and characterized at the Karlsruhe Research Accelerator KARA. KIT has supported these TA experiments by several simulations and experiments campaigns. With injection of 500 MeV bunches into different negative alpha optics, electron beams up to 22 mA current were operated with different tunes and chromaticity. Measurements of the injection orbit at low and negative alpha condition, the bunch length with a

streak camera and the THz emission dynamics as function of alpha, beam characterization, dynamics studies, and the study of collective effects were done.

The expected synchrotron radiation spectrum of FCC is a close match to that provided by the KIT light source, making its storage ring KARA an ideal choice to test FCC components. CERN and KIT loaded the BESTEX beamline of CERN at KARA with different up to 2-meter mock-ups to examine different components for the Future Circular Collider FCC-hh. CERN and INFN studied the photon and electron desorption by exposing beam-screen prototypes in BESTEX to significant levels of synchrotron radiation with a realistic energy spectrum at KIT, comparable to the operation conditions at the hadron collider.

1.2 KIT-FLUTE

To detect short electron bunches using split ring resonators (SRR), the equipment was installed at FLUTE in collaboration with the Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI, Villigen, CH), the University of Bern (CH). The experimental setup was prepared with a vacuum chamber with integrated remote tables at PSI, the University of Bern provided SRR structures and the layout for the THz setup. The LLRF system for FLUTE was set up in a collaboration of DESY and KIT. FLUTE diagnostic equipment such as BPMs, ICT, screen, Faraday cup and an energy spectrometer detected electron bunches from 10 to 200 pC with energies from 4 to 7 MeV. Cathode centre, laser beam for UV light on the cathode as well as THz light on the SRR, the diagnostic components, the microstructured SRR, pinholes from 50 to 1000 μm and several screens were measured and aligned with an optical laser system via a pinhole cathode to the central axis of the machine. Extensive series of experiments were performed varying the laser power, laser spot size, laser spot position, THz generation and focus position, cathode surface quality, RF power, RF phase, electron beam energy, electron beam size, etc. Evaluation of the final April 2022 experimental campaign is ongoing. THz radiation was detected for the adjustment with a PTB calibrated power meter and for the SRR experiment using a fast Schottky diode.

1.3 IPHI

After upgrading the IPHI cooling system in 2017 and restarting the beam in December 2017, the IPHI beam was used for internal experiments in Spring 2018 and an experiment within the ARIES program took place only in October 2018. The experiment consisted in testing a Beam Position Monitor (BPM) designed by ESS Bilbao (Spain) for the European Spallation Source (ESS).

In 2019, the activity at IPHI was oriented towards the tests of Beryllium targets for neutron production as an R&D in view of a possible French compact neutron source (SONATE project). Five targets were tested at a beam power between 1 and 3.5 kW for a total duration of about 250 hours in 2019 – 2020. A high power target was installed in 2021 and tested at 30 kW beginning of 2022.

Although performed outside the ARIES Transnational Access program, these tests are important in view of the development of Compact Accelerator-based Neutron Sources in Europe.

1.4 SINBAD

In the first TNA experiment (PSI, Switzerland) a next-generation polygonal nano-wire scanner (PNWS) and reverse tomography techniques was used to characterize the high-brightness bunches at ARES in 2D with extremely high resolution. In the frame of the project the new polygonal nano-wire scanner was benchmarked with other diagnostics devices. For the first time a 4D mapping of the electron beam was performed along the beam trajectory at a dielectric laser accelerator. The controls and evaluation software of PNWS was successfully integrated into the ARES systems. Furthermore, the test showed a discrepancy between the measurement of the PNWS and a standard screen which could then be traced to an issue with the reflections of the scintillators of the screen, allowing the correction of this device in the future. Lastly, the beamtime established a procedure for a faster implementation and use of the PNWS in the future.

In the second TNA experiment (EPFL, Lausanne, Switzerland) the main goal was to experimentally study the colour centres created in nitrogen-rich diamond materials using ultra-high energy electron irradiation (155 MeV) and a standardized annealing process. In particular, among other diamond colour centres the interested lies in nitrogen-vacancy (NV) centres, for their great potentialities in quantum sensing applications. Previous works considered irradiation energies below 15 MeV: this work will give new insights into the NV formation process in a previously unexplored regime and potentially offer new ways to improve the sensitivity of NV-based measurements.

The single crystal diamond sample was irradiated with a beam diameter around 200 μ m. The irradiation lasted 96 hours, to reach an irradiation dose of $1.5 \cdot 10^{18} e/cm^2$, comparable with commonly used doses in the literature at lower energies. After the irradiation the sample was characterized at EPFL using 3 main techniques: photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopy (excitation at 532nm), CW-Optically detected magnetic resonance (ODMR), Raman spectroscopy (excitation at 785nm). Further analysis on the acquired data are ongoing.

1.5 VELA

For the initial TNA experiment, a team led by PSI looked at proof-of-principle tests on THz-driven deflector structures, intended as a first step towards the development of longitudinal beam diagnostics in the attosecond regime. Using the UHV sample chamber within Beam Area 1 of the VELA/CLARA facility, the team installed a split ring THz resonator system. The key technical challenges were to ensure the correct alignment of the VELA/CLARA electron beam through the deflector interaction point and the synchronisation of the electron beam to the laser/THz source, which were successfully demonstrated.

The following TNA access, led by researchers from DESY, looked at developing high resolution time-of-arrival diagnostics through the observation of plasma afterglow. These experiments, enabled through optimal synchronisation and alignment of the laser and electron beams with a gas jet, demonstrated the first interaction of the accelerated VELA/CLARA electron beam with a laser-ionized plasma. The initial experimental run in 2019 was supplemented with an additional allocation in late-2021 to investigate plasma microlensing at high gas/plasma densities.

The concluding TNA experiment, performed shortly before the end of the programme, allowed investigators led by PSI to evaluate the performance of a hybrid pixel detector for electron diffraction at MeV energies. Analysis is ongoing.

4. List of publications linked to Transnational Access activities

TA Project Acronym	Publication Year	Authors	Title	References	Publication type	Peer reviewed	DOI	Open Access
ARIES-KIT-ANKA-2018-04	2018	P. Schreiber et al.	Status of Operation with Negative Momentum Compaction at KARA	IPAC 2019	Conference proceedings	yes	https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2019-MOPTS017	yes
ARIES-KIT-FLUTE-2018-01 and ARIES-KIT-FLUTE-2018-02	2019	M. J. Nasse et al.	First Electron Beam at the Linear Accelerator FLUTE at KIT	IPAC 2019	Conference proceedings	yes	https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2019-MOPTS018	yes
ARIES-KIT-FLUTE-2018-01 and ARIES-KIT-FLUTE-2018-02	2019	T. Schmelzer et al.	Diagnostics and First Beam Measurements at FLUTE	IPAC 2019	Conference proceedings	yes	doi:10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2019-WEPGW01	yes
ARIES-KIT-ANKA-2018-04	2020	P. Schreiber et al.	Status of negative momentum compaction operation at KARA	CERN Yellow Reports: Conference Proceedings, vol. Vol. 9, p. 297 Pages, Dec. 2020	Conference proceeding	No	https://doi.org/10.23732/CYRCP-2020-009.297	Yes

**TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS TO ELECTRON AND PROTON
BEAM TESTING FACILITIES**

Date: 30/06/2022

ARIES_KIT_FL UTE-2018-01 and ARIES-KIT- FLUTE-2018-02	2021	M. Nabinger, E. Bründermann, S. Funkner, B. Härer, A.-S. Müller, M.J. Nasse, G. Niehues, R. Ruprecht, J. Schäfer, T. Schmelzer, N. Smale	Efficient terahertz generation by tilted-pulse- front pumping in lithium niobate for the split-ring resonator experiment at flute	Int. Particle Accelerator Conf. IPAC2021	Conference proceeding (video)	No	doi:10.5445/I R/1000137372	Yes
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Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
KARA	KARlsruhe Research Accelerator
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany
FLUTE	Far Infrared Linac and Test Experiment (Ferninfrarot-, Linac- und Test-Experiment in German)
IPHI	High-intensity Proton Injector
CEA	Commissariat à l'Énergie Atomique et aux Énergies Alternatives, France
SINBAD	Short INnovative Bunches and Accelerators
DESY	Deutsche Elektronen-SYNchrotron, Germany
ARES	Accelerator Research Experiment at SINBAD
VELA	Versatile Electron Linear Accelerator
STFC	Science and Technology Facilities Council, UKRI, United Kingdom
CERN	Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire, European Organization for Nuclear Research
TA	Transnational Access
CLIC	Compact Linear Collider
ARIES	Accelerator Research and Innovation for European Science and Society
SOLEIL	Source optimisée de lumière d'énergie intermédiaire du LURE, France
PSI	Paul Scherrer Institut, Switzerland
Oxford	University of Oxford & Oxford University Innovation, United Kingdom
FCC	Future Circular Collider
BESTEX	BEam Screen Test bench EXperiment
SRR	Spilt Ring Resonator
BPM	Beam Position Monitor
ICT	Integrated Current Transformer
RF	Radio Frequency
IPAC	International Particle Accelerator Conference